

ARTIFICIAL HAIR SENSORS FROM STRUCTURAL MICROFIBERS AND CNT ARRAYS FOR SENSING AIR FLOW OR MECHANICAL SHEAR

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ABSTRACT

Here we discuss the characterization and modeling of a relatively new class of embedded artificial hair sensors. The sensors take advantage of the mechanical properties of structural S2 glass microfibers as the hair element and the electromechanical properties of self-aligned carbon nanotube arrays to rapidly transduce small changes in force or displacement into changes in resistance. While traditionally envisioned for air flow sensing, this approach can also provide fundamental understanding of the electrical and mechanical properties of fuzzy fibers and may have additional applications to structural monitoring. The materials of the entire sensor are chosen to survive CNT synthesis conditions (700°C, inert atmosphere) as well as the typical processing and operating conditions for aerospace composite skin materials. Each sensor is individually contained within a small footprint. While other hair sensor designs suffer from reduction in bandwidth due to mechanical coupling of the hair by the transducer, our models indicate that the stiffness of the distributed CNT array supporting the S2 fiber is high relative to the low mass of the fiber. As a result the resonance frequency of the hair is maximized as if rigidly fixed at its base (e.g. the opening of the pore), yet the base of the hair deflects enough to induce a resistance change. In comparison to other published

results, we believe these sensors display the highest sensitivity for air velocities less than 10 m/s. The electromechanical responses of the sensors to both point loads and to the distributed loads from airflow are compared, and their responses under both quasi-static and dynamic conditions are correlated to the mechanical properties of the hair and nanotubes. Employing the sensors to measure the mechanical strain in composites is also investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Artificial hair sensors in which the deflection of a high aspect ratio, minimally obtrusive shaft is transduced into a detectable response are inspired by natural hair sensors such as those found on spiders, crickets, locusts, and bats[1-4]. In contrast to conventional localized sensors, the ability to distribute hair sensors over an aircraft surface would enable spatial air flow pattern detection for envisioned applications such as attitude control, heading determination, self-stabilization, and sideslip regulation[5-7]. Their small volume and low power consumption make them well suited for air flow detection on low-Reynolds-number flyers. These qualities are also attractive for mechanical sensors that can be embedded in structural materials such as composites. Ideal sensors for either application will exhibit high sensitivity while being mechanically robust enough to be embedded in a wing or composite structure.

Carbon nanotubes (CNT) are promising candidates for embedded sensing elements for their multifunctional properties, variable forms, and compatibility with other materials. They can self-assemble during CVD synthesis to become aligned normal to the growth surface into what has been referred to as a foam, a forest, or an array. Synthesis of these nanotube arrays on structural microfibers – in this case aligned radially from the fiber surface – has been investigated[8-10], and composites of these “fuzzy fibers” can have improved electrical and thermal conductivity[11] and enhanced structural properties such as toughness[12, 13] and interlaminar shear[14-16]. While not yet fully predicted, the nanotube arrays also exhibit piezoresistivity. CNT arrays on glass fibers have been demonstrated as embedded strain sensors in composites when expanded along the fiber[17, 18]. When compressed against a metalized surface, CNT arrays on planar substrates have been shown to have a large decrease in resistance that is attributed to changes both in the CNT-metal contact resistance and bulk CNT array piezoresistivity[19-21]. The mechanical properties of planar CNT arrays have also been directly characterized[21-28], but those for CNT arrays on fibers have been less reported.

Here we discuss the characterization and modeling of a relatively new class of embedded artificial hair sensors. Structural glass microfibers with high specific stiffness serve as the hair element, and the piezoresistive nanotube array on the fibers transduce the deflection of the hair into changes in resistance when compressed inside the metal coated glass pore[10, 29, 30]. We demonstrate the qualitative similarity in response to quasi-static deflections due a point load in a laboratory-scale setup and the distributed load response experienced within an air flow. These point load deflections are fitted to a model treating the nanotube support as an elastic base, and the stiffness of the radial nanotube array is derived. The resonance frequencies of the sensor are found by perturbing a sensor at acoustic frequencies to probe the dynamic response of the sensors. We show these frequencies to agree with those predicted for an elastic base if the stiffness from the quasi-static measurements is used. They also agree with models that assume the hair is fixed at the transducer, suggesting the stiffness of the nanotubes to be high relative to the mass of the glass fiber. Finally, we introduce a new application for these deflection-based sensors as shear sensors by embedding a sensor within a bonded composite and measuring the displacement between adherends in a lap shear test.

2 FUZZY FIBER ARTIFICIAL HAIR SENSOR

A cross-sectional schematic of these hair-in-pore sensors is shown in Figure 1a. The hairs are glass microfibers (AGY 933 S-2) of radius $4.5 \mu\text{m}$ (r) with bending stiffness (EI) of 28 Nm^2 and density (ρ) of 2580 kg/m^3 according to the manufacturer. The pore for the hair is a glass microcapillary of inner radius (R) $12.5 \mu\text{m}$, cut and polished to a final length of 1.2 mm. Gold electrodes were deposited on each end of the capillaries by sputtering at an angle such that the gold coats the inside walls of the

capillaries to a depth approximately equal to twice the diameter and is electrically continuous across the top face of the capillary and partially down the sides as shown in Figure 1a. The glass fibers were inserted into the microcapillaries and the entire assemblies were subjected to the CNT synthesis by CVD. The CNTs grow radially from the alumina-coated glass fiber surface as a self-aligned, entangled array both inside and external to the capillary. As it grows, the CNT array self-positions the glass fiber to the radial center of the capillary. Further details of the MEMs-free fabrication process are given elsewhere [10, 29, 30].

Figure 1: (a) Cross-sectional schematic of nanotube-microfiber artificial hair sensor (not to scale). (b) The response of Sensor 1 to a varying point load in a bench-top test fixture with $L_p = 800 \mu\text{m}$ and the response of the same sensor to the distributed steady aerodynamic forces of air at varying velocities inside a plane wave tube.

After CNT synthesis the hair is cut flush with the bottom of the capillary where it is secured with epoxy. In operation, the length of fiber extending from the top of the capillary – referred to here as the external length (L_E) – is subjected to external forces such as from air flow, with the additional length of the capillary accounting for the total length (L_T) of the fiber. The CNT array is grown to at least fill the space between the fiber and capillary at the capillary opening. Outside the capillary the total CNT-fiber diameter can be larger than the inner capillary diameter. The nanotubes add additional mass to the fiber, increasing the mass per length (ρ_A) from at least $1.6 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg/m}$ for the bare glass fiber to an estimated upper limit of $2.9 \times 10^{-7} \text{ kg/m}$ for the fuzzy fiber.

3 QUASI-STATIC RESPONSE

The response of Sensor 1 to quasi-static deflection by two methods is shown in Figure 1b. The change in the resistance was measured in a benchtop test fixture, deflecting the hair by a distance δ at a point $800 \mu\text{m}$ along the fiber from the capillary opening. The sensitivity is observed to be small for δ up to $25 \mu\text{m}$ followed by large changes for increasing δ up to about $100 \mu\text{m}$. The response of the sensor to steady air flow inside a plane wave tube was also measured. Similar to the point load response, the change in resistance to increasing air flow velocity is nearly zero for low air speeds up to about 1.2 m/s followed by a region of high sensitivity before plateauing at about $5 \text{ k}\Omega$ of total resistance change around 3 m/s . This overall change in response of about 5% per m/s of air speed is similar to the 1% per m/s value reported for the sensitivity previously, both larger than the 0.1% per m/s more typical of artificial hair sensors[30].

Maschmann *et al.* compressed forests of CNTs grown on planar substrates onto a substrate with electrodes and measured the electrical contact resistance and compression modulus[19]. A similar S-shaped change in the resistance with increasing stress or strain was observed, with small changes in resistance at strains up to about 1% followed by a region of high sensitivity before the resistance saturates at strains of 2 to 15% .

To characterize the strain and compression modulus of the CNTs within the capillary, the external curvature of the hair with varying load was experimentally characterized and modelled similar to the method reported by Phillips *et al.*[29]. A point load was applied to the hair of the sensor at a position 950 μm from the capillary opening in ten increments. Optical images of the resulting bending and displacement of the hair are shown for some of the loads in Figure 2a, and the profiles extracted from these images are shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 2: (a) Optical images of the hair in response to increasing point loads with indicated test number. The hair is partially obscured by the knife blade deflecting the hair. The capillary opening is to the left. (b) Profiles of the hair extracted from the optical images relative to the hair before deflection and the fit of the profiles to a static elastic base model. (c) The electrical response of the sensor to increasing load (numbered) plotted against the maximum strain experienced by the CNTs calculated from the fit results. Error bars are one standard deviation.

The deflection of the CNT-supported hair in response to such quasi-statically changing loads can be modelled as a cantilevered beam with a tip that is free to move and supported by an elastic base inside the capillary. In the case of the point load, the hair experiences a load P at a distance $x = L_p$ from the capillary opening which is balanced by the force per length $ky(x)$ along the hair inside the capillary where k is the stiffness per length of the elastic base and $y(x)$ is the deflection of the hair. Assuming the deflection of the hair is nearly zero through much of the bottom section of the capillary, this static elastic base model results in two equations for the bending of the beam

$$y(x) = -\frac{P}{6EI}x^3 + \frac{L_p P}{2EI}x^2 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\bigg|_{x=0}\right)x + y_0 \text{ for } x \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

$$y(x) = \frac{2\psi \exp(\psi x)}{k} [P \cos(\psi x) + L_p P \psi (\cos(\psi x) + \sin(\psi x))] \text{ for } x \leq 0 \quad (2)$$

where EI is the bending stiffness of the fiber and ψ is given by

$$\psi = \sqrt[4]{\frac{k}{4EI}}. \quad (3)$$

The deflection of the fiber and slope of the deflection must be equal for the two deflection equations at the opening of the capillary ($x = 0$). Differing from Phillips *et al.* we consider L_p to be known and assume k to be constant as the load is varied. This leaves three independent variables per deflection and one variable k that can be fit across all the deflections.

The resulting best fit of the deflections to the solution of Equations 1 and 2 are plotted with the corresponding optical images in Figure 2a. The coefficient of determination R^2 of the fit is 0.996 with a stiffness constant k of 6.5 MN/m^2 . The electrical response of the sensor is plotted against both the deflection of the hair at the opening and the maximum strain experienced by the CNT array at the opening in Figure 2b. The highest sensitivity is observed for strains at the pore opening of 2 to 8% similar to the results reported for planar arrays.

To relate this two dimensional model and stiffness constant to the real case of a round fiber inside a round capillary, we consider a slice of unit length inside the capillary (Fig. 3). The elastic base model assumes the force per length on this fiber segment is linear with its vertical displacement y by the factor k . The magnitude of axial compression (z) of the nanotubes around the perimeter depends on their angular location θ . Ignoring shear and bending of the nanotubes and assuming no adhesion to the sidewalls or pre-compression of the array, the nanotubes above the fiber exert no force on the fiber while the section of nanotube below the fiber at angle θ exert a force per area of

$$\frac{\kappa}{R-r} z(\theta, y) \quad (4)$$

where κ , r , and R are the compression modulus of the carbon nanotube array, the radius of the glass fiber, and the inner radius of the capillary, respectively. The horizontal components of this force cancel from one side to the other, so only the vertical component contributes.

Figure 3: (a) A unit-length cross-section of the glass fiber coated with a CNT array inside the capillary before and after deflection of the glass fiber. (b) The force diagram for the compressed section of CNT array at position theta.

The magnitude of the compression of the nanotubes is related to the vertical displacement of the fiber by

$$z(\theta, y) = R + y \cos(\theta) - \sqrt{R^2 - y^2} (1 - \cos(2\theta)). \quad (5)$$

Integrating the force per area over the bottom half of the fiber perimeter gives the force per length:

$$\frac{\kappa r \pi y}{2(R-r)} - \frac{\kappa r}{(R-r)} \left(\sqrt{R^2 - y^2} - 2R + \frac{R^2}{y} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{y}{\sqrt{R^2 - y^2}} \right) \right). \quad (6)$$

This is equivalent to force per length ky from the elastic base model. For small strains ($y \ll R$), the second term of Equation 6 goes to zero and the force per length is linearly proportional to the vertical displacement of the hair, or

$$k \approx \frac{\kappa r \pi}{2(R-r)}. \quad (7)$$

For a stiffness constant (k) of 6.5 MN/m^2 , the corresponding compressive modulus (κ) from this relationship is 7.3 MPa which is within the range reported in literature^[19, 25, 31] for arrays grown on planar substrates but at the upper end of that range. This can be expected since inclusion of additional terms in Equation 6 and inclusion of additional forces from the nanotubes (shear, adhesion, etc) would lower these estimated values of κ . The modulus of these CNT arrays could also be high since the planar measurements were for unrestricted nanotube growth and the CNT arrays in the sensors are likely of higher density since the nanotubes were restricted to the volume of the capillary.

4 DYNAMIC RESPONSE

To determine the resonance properties of the sensors we characterized their response to oscillating air flows. A compression driver modulates the air flow in the plane wave tube and a microphone above the hair at the same position along the tube detects the resulting sound pressure. A function generator sends a sinusoidal signal of a specific frequency to the compression driver, and the amplitude is determined by PID such that the sound pressure amplitude is held constant as the frequency is changed.

The response of Sensor 2 with an external hair length of 4.37 mm (5.57 mm total length) in response to oscillating air flow with RMS sound pressure amplitude of 53 Pa is shown in Figure 4a. Three peaks in the magnitude of the resistance change are observed corresponding to the first three modes of the hair. The resonance frequencies are determined by fitting each peak to a Lorentzian curve, with the center of the fit peaks found to be at 273 , 1872 , and 5101 Hz respectively.

Figure 4: (a) The amplitude of the response of Sensor 2 to varying frequency of air flow at constant sinusoidal sound pressure amplitude. The peaks correspond to the first three resonance modes of the hair sensor. (b) The measured and predicted resonance frequencies versus mode number.

The natural frequencies f_n for a vibrating Euler-Bernoulli beam only supported at one or both ends are known to be

$$f_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\alpha_n^2}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A}} \quad (8)$$

where L is the length of the beam and the α_n are determined from the boundary conditions of the beam. Assuming a beam that is free at one end and fixed at the other (slope = 0), the first three α_n are 1.875, 4.694, and 7.854. The measured resonance frequencies are well fit to this model using these “fixed base” values of α_n (Fig. 4). Assuming L to be the external length of the hair ($L = L_E = 4.37$ mm) and EI to be the bending stiffness of the glass fiber, the mass per length corresponding to the best fit is 2.9×10^{-7} kg/m which is within the predicted range.

While this model appears to accurately account for the resonance frequencies of the system, it doesn't give insight into the mechanical role of the nanotubes supporting the fiber inside the capillary. Nor does such a fixed base model capture the operation of the sensor since compression of the CNT array against the electrode by movement of the fiber at the opening (the “base”) is neglected. So we again consider an elastic base scenario, this time adding a stiffness constant k to the time-varying Euler-beam equation:

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 y(x,t)}{\partial x^4} + ky(x,t) + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 y(x,t)}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where k is zero outside the capillary ($x \geq 0$). This “partial elastic base” condition can be solved by again treating the two sections of the beam independently and matching the solutions at the opening of the capillary. The resonance frequencies are found from the relationship

$$f_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\beta_n^2}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A}} \right)^2 + \frac{k}{\rho A}} \quad (10)$$

where L is now the total length of the hair ($L = L_T = 5.57$ mm) and the β_n are determined from the boundary conditions. In this case for these devices, the hair is modeled as having a free end outside of the capillary and a fixed end at the bottom of the capillary.

In the absence of an elastic base ($k=0$), the β_n are identical to the α_n in Equation 8 and the natural frequencies are the same as those found from the fixed base model but with $L = L_T$ rather than $L = L_E$. Eisenberger et al. predicted that the resonance frequencies will be increased from these minimum frequencies if k is increased, tending asymptotically to the $L = L_E$ fixed base natural frequencies[32]. The two models are equivalent for an infinite value of k in the elastic base model.

The fit of the resonance frequencies to the elastic base model is also shown in Figure 3b using the k predicted by the static measurements and with ρA again as the fit parameter. The mass per length (2.7×10^{-7} kg/m) is slightly lower than the fixed base result but still within the expected range. There is little difference between the resonance frequencies from the two models and the measured resonance frequencies which indicates that they are at the asymptotic limit of the elastic base model and the stiffness constant k is large relative to the mass per length of the hair.

4 MECHANICAL SHEAR SENSING

Here we consider these hair sensors for detecting the displacement due to shear in a composite or bonded joint. Lap shear coupons 25.4 mm wide were prepared by bonding two pieces of 1.61 mm thick fiberglass epoxy composite adherends (Sabic G10/FR4) with an epoxy adhesive (Hardman Red #04001). Wire spacers in the bond were used to define an adhesive thickness of 0.254 mm. A small hole was drilled through the thickness of the adherends in the bond region for inserting the sensor. The hole radius was 0.286 mm through most of the thickness but narrowed to 0.171 mm at the bond line to provide a stop for the top edge of the capillary and provide a contact point for the hair (Fig. 5a). The response of Sensor 3 to point loads applied at 1 mm from the capillary opening were previously characterized, so the same contact point was chosen within the coupon. Small wires were attached to the top and bottom electrodes of the sensor before inserting it (Fig. 5b).

Figure 5: (a) Cross-section schematic of the lap shear coupon and embedded hair sensor. (b) Optical image of the hair sensor. (c) The lap shear coupon with embedded hair sensor. (d) The cyclic tensile load and corresponding relative displacement of the adherends as indicated by the hair sensor.

For mechanical testing (Fig. 5c) the sample was loaded in tension to 1020 N and then cycled at a rate of 0.05 Hz between 270 N and 1780 N, or about 10% to 67% of the expected maximum load. The resistance change of the sensor was measured and translated to displacement using the results from the point load measurements. The signals from the load cell and the hair cell were correlated to the nearest second and are plotted in Figure 5d.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Artificial hair sensors were demonstrated using high specific stiffness glass microfibers as the hair element and piezoresistive, self-aligned carbon nanotube arrays as the mechanical support and transducing element. The response to quasi-static deflections due a point load in a laboratory-scale setup and the distributed load response within an air flow both showed an S-shaped response. The shape of the curve and dependence on the strain of the nanotubes is also similar to the results reported elsewhere for compression of planar nanotubes. While the decrease in resistance can be expected, the nature of this curve shape and strain dependence is not yet well understood.

Both the static and the vibrational elastic base models predict that lowering the stiffness of the nanotube support would increase the deflection of the hair at the opening for a given airflow or deflection, presumably increasing the sensitivity. The resonance frequencies would also be decreased, but Eisenberger et al. show this occurs first and more quickly for the higher modes. The agreement of the fixed base model with the resonance frequencies even out to the third mode suggests the stiffness could be decreased without significant changes to the first-resonance bandwidth. Conversely, increasing the nanotube stiffness would decrease the deflection of the hair at the base and increase the range of the sensor with little change to the resonance frequencies.

Even with current fabrication methods, the normalized response to air flow was observed to be larger than other published sensors and as high as 5% change per m/s of air speed. If considered as a strain sensor, the resistance of Sensor 2 decreased by about 25% when the calculated strain on the nanotubes at the opening of the sensor was 10%. This gauge factor of 2.5 is a relatively modest value, but conventional strain sensors cannot be used to measure out-of-plane motion such as shear. A successful measurement of the relative displacement in a lap shear coupon was demonstrated here for the first time even though the resistance change was only about 0.1%. Larger sensitivities similar to those demonstrated in the air flow measurements should be achievable by moving the point of displacement on the hair closer to the bond line.

While evaluated against applications for air flow sensing and mechanical shear sensing, characterization of the sensors by these methods provides fundamental understanding of the

mechanical properties of fuzzy fibers. The elastic base stiffness constant of the radial nanotube array supporting the glass fiber was determined to be 6.5 MN/m² by fitting the static bending profile of the hair in response to point loads. This stiffness constant was found to correspond to a compression modulus for the nanotube array of 7.3 MPa. The model assumed the stiffness of the elastic base to be linear with the displacement of the hair. Even accounting for the radial arrangement of the nanotubes around the fiber, we showed this linear assumption to hold for small displacements and assuming the compression modulus to be linear. Current efforts are focused on improving the accuracy of the profile measurements and compression modulus calculations in which case it may be necessary to evaluate the model with additional dependencies on displacement corresponding to additional terms in Equation 6.

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